

Program Committee Poll - Week 2

Desired input from the PC committee due Mar 25, 2024. Submissions should be completed before the due date. This form will gather your input for our list of invited speakers.

* Indicates required question

1. Please enter your first and last name. *

2. Please enter your work email address. *

Potential Invited Speaker

Who would you recommend as an invited speaker? The speaker should be able to address multiple software categories and lifecycle stages.

3. Please indicate their name here. *

4. Please indicate their work email here. *

5. Please indicate which software categories they could address with expertise. *

Check all that apply.

- Mission-related software
- Code associated with research (e.g. for publications)
- Data repository software (e.g. infrastructure software, cloud services, software environments)
- Archiving software (in a FAIR manner, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>)
- Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy, Astropy)
- Models, simulations, and related software (including pre and post processing and visualization codes)
- ML/AI codes
- General analysis software for wide use (e.g. SciPy)
- Infrastructure as code, and web and cloud applications (e.g. cloud platforms and services)
- High performance computing

6. Please indicate which lifecycle stages they could address with expertise. *

Check all that apply.

- Discovery vs acquisition vs collaboration for software
- Funding software effectively
- Designing/developing software
- Developing vs contributing to software
- When to choose open or closed software?
- Releasing software (e.g. the Software Release Authorization process)
- Maintaining software, confirming reproducibility/reusability
- Retiring software vs modernizing software
- Building, fostering, and managing software communities and collaborations
- Security and supply chain risk management
- Complying with policies (e.g. NPR 1750, NASA policies, etc)
- Formulating and aligning with best practices and standards for software

7. Please enter any other helpful information here.

8. Would you prefer the invitation email to come from NASA Headquarters, or would you prefer to send the email?

Mark only one oval.

From NASA HQ.

From me.

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